

Degradation Characteristics of SiC Whisker

Reinforced Al Composites

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ABSTRACT: Mechanical properties of silicone carbide whisker reinforced aluminum 6061 alloy matrix composites (SiCw/Al) degraded by thermal cycling and isothermal exposure were examined by tensile tests and hardness measurement. Fracture features were observed using a scanning electron microscope in order to verify the fracture mechanism of thermally cycled (TC) and isothermally exposed (IE) SiCw/Al. Moreover, the experimental results were verified theoretically using shear-lag model for discontinuous fiber composites. Proof stress and ultimate tensile strength of the TC-SiCw/Al dramatically decreased compared with the original SiCw/Al in opposition to the IE-SiCw/Al that had almost all of tensile strengths of the original one. These results were related to microstructural changing of SiCw/Al occurred during thermal cycling or isothermal exposure. Tensile strengths of the TC- and IE-SiCw/Al had a certain relation with the corresponding hardness. Empirical equation about such a relation was obtained by statistical analysis. The results obtained from calculation based on shear-lag model were in agreement with experimental results.

Keywords: SiCw/Al, thermally cycled degradation, isothermally exposed degradation, tensile strengths, shear-lag model

INTRODUCTION

Development of eco-materials, reduction of manufacturing cost and increase of reliability of the structural materials were one of main projects among the researchers who study material strength of the materials or produce new materials. Besides, integrity assessment of materials must be an important thing to increase the reliability of structural materials. Particularly, assessment of degradation characteristics in the structural materials including composites may be very important data in the viewpoint of developing new advanced materials and gives a direct certain helping to the industrial fields where structural materials are actually used. Because structural materials used as diverse shapes in the industrial fields will gradually lose

mechanical properties allowed at the time of design together with use time. Such a degradation phenomenon was caused by various factors such as radiation, temperature, corrosion etc. Moreover, recently, use of the composites has been increasing in the automobile and aerospace industries as a central figure explosively. So, importance of integrity assessment in the composites i.e. the necessity of degradation characteristics assessment of the composites has increased. However, such researches on composites especially, metal matrix composites did not have done sufficiently up to now. Authors already reported research results assessing the mechanical properties of the SiCp/Al degraded by thermal cycling and isothermal exposure and proposed the empirical equation to be able to predict the mechanical properties of the thermally degraded SiCp/Al using simple hardness measurement [1-2]. In the present study, as a series of researches about degradation characteristics of the SiC/Al composites degraded by thermal cycling and isothermal exposure, mechanical properties of the silicone carbide whisker reinforced Al composites degraded by thermal cycling and isothermal exposure were examined using tensile tests and micro hardness measurement.

MATERIALS AND PROCEDURES

Silicone carbide (SiC) whisker reinforced AA6061 composites (SiCw/Al) with 25% whisker volume fraction were used for this study. Size of SiC whiskers was $0.5\mu\text{m}\sim 1\mu\text{m}$ in diameter and $10\mu\text{m}\sim 20\mu\text{m}$ in length. The SiCw/Al composites were fabricated by Mitsubishi Light Metal Company, Japan using high-pressure infiltration followed by hot extrusion. After then, they were solution treated and artificially aged. Aluminum 6061 Alloy (AA6061) was manufactured by the same method as the SiCw/Al for comparison.

Two artificially degraded SiCw/Al composites were prepared using an electric furnace with PID temperature controller. Some SiCw/Al and AA6061 were degraded by thermal cycling (TC),

Figure1. Research flowchart to examine the mechanical properties of the TC- and IE-SiCw/Al

which was repeated 100 times from 200°C to 300°C. The other SiCw/Al and AA6061 were degraded by isothermal exposure (IE), which was hold at 300°C for 80h. Since a certain standard needs for comparing the TC-SiCw/Al and IE-SiCw/Al with each other, hardness of the AA6061 was used as a standard to set the holding time in isothermal exposure. In other word, holding time, 80h was the time that the AA6061 degraded by isothermal exposure at 300°C had the same hardness as the AA6061 degraded by thermal cycling as shown in Fig. 2. Non-degraded SiCw/Al and AA6061 were designated as original SiCw/Al and AA6061, respectively. Thermally cycled and isothermally exposed SiCw/Al (or AA6061) were cooled in the furnace to stifle occurrence of residual stress, which may be generated during cooling step. Tensile tests (Autograph AGS-G, Shimadzu) were carried out under the crosshead speed of 8.33×10^{-7} m/s to fracture, using double dumbbell specimen as Figure 3, direction of which was extrusion direction of the as-received ingots. Micro Vickers hardness (hereafter noted as hardness) was measured to the square discs with 8mm width and 2mm thickness under the conditions of 150mg_f load, $7.2\text{mg}_f/\text{s}$ loading speed and 10s holding time (BUH 201, Shimadzu). Hardness was measured 10 times per specimen. The measured values were averaged. Microscopic observation of fracture surfaces for the TC- and IE-SiCw/Al was carried out using a scanning electron microscope (JSM-5410LS, Jeol).

Figure 2. Variation of hardness in the TC- and IE-AA6061

Figure 3. Tensile specimen

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile tests and hardness measurements were performed to two different artificially degraded SiCw/Al. Such results i.e. proof stresses and ultimate tensile strengths of the TC- and IE-SiCw/Al (and AA6061) are presented in Figure. 4. Variation of $\sigma_{TC,IE}/\sigma_{OR}$ is presented in Figure 5. σ is tensile strength of the SiCw/Al (or AA6061), and subscripts *TC*, *IE* and *OR* are thermally cycled, and isothermally exposed and original specimen, respectively. It was natural result that tensile strengths of the TC- and IE-AA6061 were very similar to each other due to which hardness values of the TC- and IE-AA6061 were artificially controlled during creating thermally degraded specimen. However, tensile strengths were lower in the TC-SiCw/Al than the IE-SiCw/Al. Furthermore, for the TC-SiCw/Al, reduction of proof stress (46% of the non-degraded SiCw/Al) was larger than that of ultimate tensile strength (65% of the non-degraded SiCw/Al). Such a result was attributed to interface debonding between the SiC whiskers and the matrix during repeated thermal cycling due to which mismatches of thermal expansion coefficients of the SiC whiskers and the matrix were large [3-4]. On the other hand, the IE-SiCw/Al had more than 87% of tensile strengths of the original one. This may relate to softening of the matrix due to which it was reported that the amount of intermetallic compounds or precipitates in the matrix is changed at before and after 300°C, temperature used for isothermal exposure of the present study [5]. It was checked that the influence of thermal degradation on the mechanical properties of the SiCw/Al differs by thermal pattern.

Since it has known that there exists a certain relation between tensile strengths and the corresponding hardness in the ordinary structural materials, variation of tensile strengths as a function of the corresponding hardness is presented in Figure 6. Though generally, the relation of the $\sigma-H_v$ is plotted in the normal graph, log-normal graph was used for describing the relation of the $\sigma-H_v$ in the TC- and IE-SiCw/Al owing to great difference of tensile strengths between the TC- and IE-SiCw/Al. Statistical analysis was performed to such relations using second polynomial equation. The coefficient of determination, R^2 , was over 0.93 for any case. As the

above results, tensile strengths of thermally degraded SiCw/Al had a certain linear relation with the corresponding hardness regardless of thermal patterns.

In order to verify such experimental results theoretically, the critical aspect ratio of the SiC whiskers, S_c and critical length of the SiC whiskers, l_c were calculated in the original, IE- and TC-SiCw/Al using shear-lag model for discontinuous fiber reinforced metal composites [6-7]. The calculation using shear-lag method was carried out under the following assumptions; SiC whiskers are distributed uniformly in the SiCw/Al composites. Interfacial shear stress between the SiC whiskers and matrix, τ , is a constant in each case.

$$\sigma_c = \left(1 - \frac{l_c}{2l}\right)\sigma_w V_f + \sigma_m V_m \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{l_c}{d} = \frac{\sigma_w}{2\tau} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_c = \frac{\tau l}{d} V_f + \sigma_m V_m \quad (3)$$

Figure 4. Tensile stresses of the SiCw/Al as well as AA6061 degraded by thermal cycling and isothermal exposure.

In the above equations, σ is stress and subscripts c , w and m mean composite, whisker and matrix, respectively. l and d are length and diameter of whisker, respectively. S_c and l_c are critical aspect ratio and critical length of the SiC whiskers, respectively. τ is the interfacial shear stress in the SiC whisker-matrix interface.

Firstly, S_c and l_c of the original and IE-SiCw/Al were calculated by substituting the tensile strengths of the original and IE-SiCw/Al (and AA6061) obtained at the tensile tests into Eqs. (1)

Figure 5. The ratio of the tensile strengths of the TC- and IE-SiCw/Al (and AA6061) to those of the non-degraded samples.

and (2). Stress of the SiC whiskers, σ_w values of the original and IE-SiCw/Al were calculated as 1302MPa and 1234MPa, respectively. Thereby, l_c values of the original and IE-SiCw/Al were $3.37\mu\text{m}$ and $3.19\mu\text{m}$, respectively. S_c values of the original and IE-SiCw/Al were 4.5, and 4.3, respectively.

Since such values were smaller than actual S_c values of the SiC whisker (10 – 40), this means

Figure 6. The relation between tensile strengths and the corresponding hardness in the TC- and IE-SiCw/Al and AA6061.

Figure 7. Micrograph of fracture surface in the TC-SiCw/Al

that fracture of the original and IE-SiCw/Al were associated with the breakage of the SiC whiskers. On the other hand, Eq (3) was used to calculate S_c and τ values of the TC-SiCw/Al because pulled-out SiC whiskers were observed in the fracture surfaces of the TC-SiCw/Al as shown in Figure 7. The S_c and τ values calculated by Eq (3) were 24 and 27MPa, respectively. The percentage of the SiC whiskers with aspect ratio less than $S_c = 24$ was about 50% of the SiC whiskers actually used. This means that a minimum of 50% SiC whiskers can be pulled out theoretically. Moreover, the results of calculating and comparing pull-out length of the SiC whiskers, l_p with the average l_p measured directly from the micrographs of the fracture surfaces of the TC-SiCw/Al, the calculated l_p (4.5 μm) overestimated 20% than the measured l_p (3.6 μm). Theoretical results were in agreement with the experimental results.

CONCLUSION

1. The reduction in proof stress, $\sigma_{0.2\%}$ and ultimate tensile strength, σ_{UTS} was greater in the TC-SiCw/Al than in the IE-SiCw/Al.
2. The results of calculating S_c of the original, TC- and IE-SiCw/Al using a simple shear lag model for discontinuous fiber reinforced composites, it is noted that fracture reason of the original and IE-SiCw/Al was breakage of the SiC whisker while fracture of the TC-SiCw/Al come from pull-out of whisker. Besides, calculated l_p (4.5 μm) overestimated within 20% error of the actual average l_p (3.6 μm).
3. Empirical relations between proof stress, $\sigma_{0.2\%}$ (and ultimate tensile strength, σ_{UTS}) and hardness, H_v were obtained. If these empirical equations are used, tensile strengths of thermally degraded SiCw/Al will be simply calculated using simple hardness measurement, regardless of kind of degradation and fracture mechanism of the degraded SiCw/Al.

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